

УДК 612.017.1+612.43+612.45+612.46+616-092.9

DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/20358608>

NEUROENDOCRINE-IMMUNE RELATIONSHIPS IN INTACT RATS

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НЕЙРОЕНДОКРИННО-ІМУННІ ВЗАЄМОВІДНОСИНИ У ІНТАКТНИХ ЦУРІВ

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Summary/Резюме

Introduction and aim. Previously, in the process of implementing the project “Sexual differences in the parameters of the neuroendocrine-immune complex and the state of neuroendocrine-immune relationships in intact rats and exposed to stressors and adaptogens”, we analyzed such relationships for the entire sample. The aim of this study is to analyze neuroendocrine-immune relationships in intact rats of both sexes.

Material and methods. We calculated the parameters of the HRV: Mode, Amplitude of the mode and Variational scope as markers of the circulating catecholamines, sympathetic and vagal tones respectively. Among endocrine parameters determined serum levels of main adaptation hormones such as Corticosterone, Aldosterone, Testosterone, Triiodothyronine, as well as Parathyroid hormone and Calcitonin. The percentage of lymphocyte populations and the parameters of phagocytosis by neutrophils and monocytes of *Staphylococcus aureus* were determined in the blood. The Thymus and Spleen were weighed and made smears-imprints for counting Thymocytogram and Splenocytogram.

Results. The canonical correlation between neuroendocrine and immune variables was analyzed. According to the levels of the coefficient of determination R^2 , neuroendocrine factors were ranked in the following order: corticosterone (0.983), testosterone (0.869), catecholamines (0.846), sympathetic tone (0.845), triiodothyronine (0.833), PTH (0.748), vagal tone (0.641), calcitonin (0.641), and aldosterone (0.627).

Conclusion. There is a close canonical correlation between registered neuroendocrine factors and immunity parameters in intact rats.

Keywords: adaptation hormones, HRV, thymus, spleen, immunocytes of blood, phagocytosis, relationships, male and female rats.

Вступ та мета. Раніше, в процесі реалізації проекту «Статеві відмінності в параметрах нейроендокринно-імунного комплексу та стан нейроендокринно-імунних взаємозв'язків у інтактних щурів та за впливу стресорів і адаптогенів», ми проаналізували такі взаємозв'язки для всієї вибірки. Метою цього дослідження є аналіз нейроендокринно-імунних взаємозв'язків у інтактних щурів обох статей.

Матеріали та методи. Ми розраховували параметри ВСР: Моду, Амплітуду моди та Варіаційний розмах як маркери циркулюючих катехоламінів та симпатичного і вагусного тону відповідно. Серед ендокринних параметрів визначали рівні в сироватці крові основних адаптаційних гормонів, таких як кортикостерон, альдостерон, тестостерон, трийодтиронін, а також паратиреоїдного гормону та кальцитоніну. У крові визначали відсоток популяцій лімфоцитів та параметри фагоцитозу нейтрофілами та моноцитами золотистого стафілокока. Тимус та селезінку зважували та робили мазки-відбитки для підрахунку тимоцитограми та спленоцитограми.

Результати. Було проаналізовано канонічну кореляцію між нейроендокринними та імунними змінними. Відповідно до рівнів коефіцієнта детермінації R^2 , нейроендокринні фактори були ранжовані в такому порядку: кортикостерон (0,983), тестостерон (0,869), катехоламіни (0,846), симпатичний тонус (0,845), трийодтиронін (0,833), ПТГ (0,748), вагусний тонус (0,641), кальцитонін (0,641) та альдостерон (0,627).

Висновок. Існує тісна канонічна кореляція між зареєстрованими нейроендокринними факторами та параметрами імунітету у інтактних щурів.

Ключові слова: адаптаційні гормони, ВСР, тимус, селезінка, імуніцити крові, фагоцитоз, взаємозв'язки, самці та самиці щурів.

Introduction

Previously, in the process of implementing the project “Sexual differences in the parameters of the neuroendocrine-immune complex and the state of neuroendocrine-immune relationships in intact rats and exposed to stressors and adaptogens”, we analyzed such relationships for the *entire* sample (four groups) [1]. The aim of this study is to analyze neuroendocrine-immune relationships in *intact* rats of both sexes.

Material and methods

Ethics approval

All animals were kept in room having temperature $22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, and relative humidity of 44-55% under 12/12 hours light and dark cycle with standard laboratory diet and water given *ad libitum*. Studies have been conducted in accordance with the rules and requirements of the “General Principles for the Work on Animals” approved by the I National Congress on Bioethics (Kyiv, Ukraine, 2001) and agreed with the provisions of the “European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrate Animals used for Experimental and other Scientific Purposes” (Council of Europe No 123,

Strasbourg 1985), and the Law of Ukraine “On the Protection of Animals from Cruelty” of 26.02.2006. The removal of animals from the experiment was carried out under light inhalation (ether) anesthesia by decapitation. The conduct of experiments was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Bohomolets’ Institute of Physiology.

Study design and procedure

Initially, ECG under light ether anesthesia was recorded, by inserting needle electrodes under the skin of the paws. Right away the animals removed from the experiment by decapitation in order to remove the adrenal glands, thymus and spleen, as well as collect the maximum possible amount of blood in which was determined some endocrine and immune parameters.

Based on about 120 R-R intervals we calculated the parameters of the HRV: Mode (Mo), Amplitude of the mode (AMo) and Variational scope (MxDMn) as markers of the circulating Catecholamines, Sympathetic and Vagal tones respectively [2].

Among endocrine parameters determined serum levels of main adaptation hor-

mones such as Corticosterone, Aldosterone, Testosterone, Triiodothyronine, as well as Parathyroid hormone and Calcitonin (by ELISA with the use of analyzer “RT-2100C” and corresponding sets of reagents from “Alkor Bio”, XEMA Co, Ltd and DRG International Inc).

In addition, the thickness of the glomerular, fascicular, reticular and medullary zones of the adrenal glands was measured in smears under a microscope [3].

Among the immune parameters of the blood, first of all, analysis of Leukocytogram

Table 1

Regression Summary for Corticosterone, nM/L
R = 0.998; R² = 0.995; Adjusted R² = 0.983; F_(14,5) = 78; p < 10⁻⁴

N = 20		Beta	St. Err. of Beta	B	St. Err. of B	t ₍₅₎	p-level
Variables	r			Intercept	18860	2373	7,95
NK-Lymphocyt. of Blood, %	0,76	0,675	0,085	67,76	8,503	7,97	0,0005
Fibroblastes of Spleen, %	0,53	-0,795	0,129	-109,9	17,82	-6,17	0,0016
Microphages of Spleen, %	0,51	0,161	0,051	27,43	8,649	3,17	0,0248
Microb. Count of Mon., B/Ph	0,41	0,309	0,096	85,09	26,47	3,21	0,0236
Leukocytes of Blood, 10 ⁹ /L	0,37	-0,530	0,060	-33,99	3,865	-8,80	0,0003
Entropy of Splenocytogram	0,37	-1,091	0,175	-9621	1541	-6,24	0,0015
Endothelocyt. of Thymus, %	-0,76	0,700	0,173	72,74	17,99	4,04	0,0099
Phagocyt. Index of Neutr., %	-0,75	-0,883	0,113	-36,47	4,673	-7,80	0,0006
Entropy of Thymocytogram	-0,70	-2,123	0,206	-7229	702	-10,3	0,0001
Epitheliocytes of Thymus, %	-0,67	2,054	0,183	95,51	8,509	11,2	0,0001
Phagocytos. In. of Monoc., %	-0,54	-0,337	0,064	-26,88	5,069	-5,30	0,0032
Lymphoblastes of Spleen, %	-0,54	-0,572	0,063	-122,3	13,52	-9,04	0,0003
Lymphocytes of Spleen, %	-0,52	-1,743	0,232	-137,7	18,36	-7,50	0,0007
Macrophages of Thymus	-0,35	1,008	0,068	195,3	13,21	14,8	10 ⁻⁴

R = 0.998; R² = 0.995; $\chi^2_{(14)} = 59$; p < 10⁻⁶; Λ Prime = 0.005

Fig. 1. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between Corticosterone level (X-line) and Immune parameters (Y-line) in intact rats

(LCG), ie the percentage of lymphocytes (L), monocytes (M), eosinophils (Eo), basophils (Bas), rod-shaped (RN) and polymorphonuclear (PMNN) neutrophils was performed. Based on these data, the Entropy of the Leukocytogram (hLCG) was calculated according to the equation derived by Popovych [4,5,6] on the basis of the classical Shannon's [7] equation:

$$hLCG = - (L \cdot \log_2 L + M \cdot \log_2 M + Eo \cdot \log_2 Eo + Bas \cdot \log_2 Bas + RN \cdot \log_2 RN + PMNN \cdot \log_2 PMNN) / \log_2 6.$$

The percentage of theophylline-resistant (TR) and theophylline-susceptible (TS) T-lymphocytes, B-lymphocytes, plasma cells (Pla), natural killers (NK), and 0-lymphocytes were identified, as described in the manual [8].

For these components the Entropy of the Immunocytogram (hICG) was calculated by Popovych [4,5,6] equation:

$$hICG = - (TR \cdot \log_2 TR + TS \cdot \log_2 TS + B \cdot \log_2 B + Pla \cdot \log_2 Pla + NK \cdot \log_2 NK + 0L \cdot \log_2 0L) / \log_2 6.$$

In addition, we tested the reaction of blast transformation of T-Lymphocytes to phytohemagglutinin [8].

About the condition of the phagocytic function of neutrophils (microphages) and monocytes (macrophages) were judged by the phagocytosis index (percentage of cells, in which found microbes), the mi-

Regression Summary for Testosterone, nM/L
R = 0.954; R² = 0.911; Adjusted R² = 0.869; F_(6,1) = 22.1; p < 10⁻⁵

N = 20		Beta	St. Err. of Beta	B	St. Err. of B	t ₍₁₃₎	p-level
Variables	r			Intercept	517	137	3,77
Lymphocytes of Thymus, %	-0,83	-0,729	0,161	-1,397	0,308	-4,53	0,001
NK-Lymphocytes of Blood, %	-0,82	-0,489	0,129	-2,675	0,708	-3,78	0,002
B-Lymphocytes of Blood, %	-0,54	-0,268	0,095	-1,547	0,545	-2,84	0,014
Entropy of Splenocytogram	-0,50	-0,604	0,220	-290,3	105,7	-2,75	0,017
Lymphocytes of Spleen, %	0,55	-0,606	0,242	-2,611	1,043	-2,50	0,026
Phagocytosis In. of Monocyt., %	0,53	-0,391	0,138	-1,701	0,602	-2,83	0,014

R = 0.954; R² = 0.911; $\chi^2_{(6)} = 36$; p < 10⁻⁵; Λ Prime = 0.089

Fig. 2. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between Testosterone level (X-line) and Immune parameters (Y-line) in intact rats

crobial count (number of microbes absorbed by one phagocyte) and the killing index (percentage of dead microbes) for *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC N25423 F49). Based on these parameters, taking into account the absolute content of neutrophils and monocytes, their bactericidal capacity (BCC N&M) was calculated [3,9].

The Thymus and Spleen were weighed and made smears-imprints for counting Thymocytogram and Splenocytogram [9]. The components of the Thymocytogram (TCG) are lymphocytes (Lc), lymphoblastes (Lb), reticulocytes (Ret), macrophages (Mac), endotheliocytes (En), epitheliocytes (Ep), and Hassal's corpuscles (H). The Splenocytogram (SCG) includes lymphocytes (Lc), lymphoblastes (Lb), plasma cells (Pla), reticulocytes (R), macrophages (Ma), fibroblasts (F), microphages (Mi), and eosinophils (Eo) [9].

For them Shannon's Entropy was calculated too:
 $hTCG = - (Lc \cdot \log_2 Lc + Lb \cdot \log_2 Lb + Ret \cdot \log_2 Ret + Mac \cdot \log_2 Mac + En \cdot \log_2 En + Ep \cdot \log_2 Ep + H \cdot \log_2 H) / \log_2 7;$
 $hSCG = - (Lc \cdot \log_2 Lc + Lb \cdot \log_2 Lb + Pla \cdot \log_2 Pla + R \cdot \log_2 R + Ma \cdot \log_2 Ma + F \cdot \log_2 F + Mi \cdot \log_2 Mi + Eo \cdot \log_2 Eo) / \log_2 8.$

Statistical analysis

Statistical processing was performed using a software package "Microsoft Excell" and "Statistica 6.4 StatSoft Inc" (Tulsa, OK, USA).

Results and discussion

At the first stage, a matrix of correlations was created between the registered neuro-endocrine factors, on the one hand, and the

Table 3

Regression Summary for 1/Mode HRV
 R = 0.942; R² = 0.887; Adjusted R² = 0.846; F_(5,1) = 22.0; p < 10⁻⁶

N = 20		Beta	St. Err. of Beta	B	St. Err. of B	t ₍₁₄₎	p-level
Variables	r			Intercpt	-598	99	6,05
Lymphocytes of Spleen, %	-0,75	0,579	0,129	6,953	1,545	4,50	0,0005
Phagocytosis In. of Neutroph., %	-0,69	0,287	0,116	1,804	0,728	2,48	0,027
Killing Index of Neutrophils, %	-0,54	0,360	0,100	2,563	0,716	3,58	0,003
Lymphoblastes of Spleen, %	-0,51	0,493	0,112	16,02	3,650	4,39	0,0006
Fibroblastes of Spleen, %	0,51	0,379	0,140	7,962	2,939	2,71	0,017

R = 0.942; R² = 0.887; $\chi^2_{(5)} = 34$; p < 10⁻⁵; Δ Prime = 0,113
 Fig. 3. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between 1/Mode HRV (X-line) and Immune parameters (Y-line) in intact rats

Table 4

Regression Summary for AMo HRV, %
 R = 0.958; R² = 0.918; Adjusted R² = 0.845; F_(9,1) = 12.5; p = 0,0002

N = 20		Beta	St. Err. of Beta	B	St. Err. of B	t ₍₁₀₎	p-level
Variables	r			Intercpt	-2176	430	-5,06
Basophils of Blood, %	0,42	0,321	0,111	16,23	5,586	2,91	0,016
Plasmocytes of Blood, %	0,39	-0,379	0,172	-11,51	5,225	-2,20	0,052
Entropy of Splenocytogram	0,36	3,409	0,631	2154	399	5,40	0,0003
Thymus mass Index, mg/100g	0,30	0,588	0,111	1280	242	5,30	0,0003
Lymphocytes of Spleen, %	-0,43	2,365	0,522	13,39	2,954	4,53	0,0011
Reticulocytes of Thymus, %	-0,38	-0,344	0,121	-3,815	1,339	-2,85	0,017
Eosinophils of Spleen, %	-0,28	-0,933	0,211	-20,59	4,651	-4,43	0,0013
Plasmocytes of Spleen, %	-0,27	-1,124	0,194	-15,18	2,621	-5,79	0,0002
Phagocyt. Ind. of Monocytes, %	-0,27	0,605	0,205	3,462	1,171	2,96	0,014

R = 0.958; R² = 0.918; $\chi^2_{(9)} = 34$; p < 10⁻⁴; Δ Prime = 0,082
 Fig. 4. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between AMo HRV (X-line) and Immune parameters (Y-line) in intact rats

immunity parameters, on the other. Then, for each neuro-endocrine factor, a regression model was built by stepwise elimination until the maximum value of Adjusted R² was achieved.

The closest relationship was found between the morpho-functional parameters of immunocytes of the thymus, spleen, and blood and the serum level of corticosterone (Table 1 and Fig. 1).

Regression Summary for Triiodothyronine, nM/L
R = 0.955; R² = 0.912; Adjusted R² = 0.833; F_(9,1) = 11.6; p = 0.0003

N = 20		Beta	St. Err. of Beta	B	St. Err. of B	t ₍₁₀₎	p-level
Variables	r	Intercpt		41,5	7,1	5,89	0,0002
Fibroblastes of Spleen, %	-0,64	-0,504	0,151	-0,142	0,043	-3,34	0,0075
Monocytes of Blood, %	-0,41	-0,785	0,155	-0,189	0,037	-5,07	0,0005
Entropy of Leukocytogram	-0,37	0,493	0,171	5,787	2,001	2,89	0,0161
B-Lymphocytes of Blood, %	-0,36	-0,278	0,1067	-0,060	0,023	-2,61	0,0261
Rod-shaped Neutrophils, %	-0,28	-0,928	0,193	-0,564	0,117	-4,82	0,0007
Entropy of Splenocytogram	-0,27	-1,861	0,345	-33,47	6,201	-5,40	0,0003
Phagocytos. Ind. of Neutr., %	0,33	-0,300	0,136	-0,025	0,011	-2,21	0,0516
Lymphocytes of Spleen, %	0,29	-1,434	0,338	-0,231	0,054	-4,24	0,0017
Eosinophils of Spleen, %	0,26	0,430	0,137	0,270	0,086	3,13	0,0107

R = 0.955; R² = 0.912; $\chi^2_{(9)} = 33$; p = 0.0001; Δ Prime = 0.088

Fig. 5. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between Triiodothyronine level (X-line) and Immune parameters (Y-line) in intact rats

Regression Summary for PTH, pg/L
R = 0.938; R² = 0.881; Adjusted R² = 0.748; F_(10,9) = 6.65; p = 0.004

N = 20		Beta	St. Err. of Beta	B	St. Err. of B	t ₍₉₎	p-level
Variables	r	Intercpt		190	406	0,47	0,652
Blast Transformation TL, %	0,55	2,326	0,556	9,859	2,358	4,18	0,0024
Lymphocytes of Thymus, %	0,51	1,296	0,494	9,047	3,448	2,62	0,0276
Monocytes of Blood, %	0,38	0,836	0,182	19,64	4,278	4,59	0,0013
Microphages of Spleen, %	0,34	-0,769	0,263	-26,12	8,914	-2,93	0,0168
B-Lymphocytes of Blood, %	0,30	1,423	0,375	12,06	3,179	3,79	0,0043
Epitheliocytes of Thymus, %	-0,49	3,847	1,026	35,55	9,477	3,75	0,0045
Phagocyt. Index of Neutr., %	-0,46	-3,149	0,821	-25,85	6,735	-3,84	0,0040
Rod-shaped Neutrophils, %	-0,42	0,860	0,296	50,96	17,51	2,91	0,0173
Phagocytosis Ind. of Mon., %	-0,41	1,947	0,414	30,87	6,572	4,70	0,0011
Bacteric. Cap. of Mon., B/L	-0,32	-2,833	0,592	-4215	881	-4,79	0,0010

R = 0.938; R² = 0.881; $\chi^2_{(10)} = 28$; p = 0.002; Δ Prime = 0.119

Fig. 6. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between PTH level (X-line) and Immune parameters (Y-line) in intact rats

The following positions, in decreasing order of Adjusted R², were occupied by testosterone (Table 2 and Fig. 2), catecholamines (Table 3 and Fig. 3), sympathetic tone (Table 4 and Fig. 4), triiodothyronine (Table 5 and Fig. 5), parathyroid hormone (Table 6 and Fig. 6), vagal tone (Table 7 and Fig. 7), calcitonin (Ta-

ble 8 and Fig. 8), and aldosterone (Table 9 and Fig. 9).

It should be noted that the identified neuroendocrine-immune associations cannot be interpreted only as the regulatory influence of hormones and autonomic nerves on the morpho-functional state of the immune system. In fact, the connections between the nervous, endocrine and immune systems are interdependent and are implemented through neurotransmitters and cytokines, the sources of which are neurons, endocrinocytes, and immunocytes [10,11,12,13].

Quantitative assessment of neuro-endocrine-immune interactions has been performed in both rats [14,15,16,17,18] and humans [18,19,20,21].

Conclusion

There is a close canonical correlation between registered neuroendocrine factors and immunity parameters in intact rats.

In subsequent articles, already prepared for publication, it will be shown that both stressors and adaptogens affect the strength of neuroendocrine-immune interactions to one degree or another.

Acknowledgments

We express sincere gratitude to Volodymyra R. Bilas, PhD, senior researcher, formerly senior researcher of Bohomolets Institute of Physiology, for help in carry out of immune

analyses.

Declarations

Funding: No funding

Conflicts of interest: The authors declare no competing interests.

Data availability: The datasets used and/

Regression Summary for MxDMn HRV, msec
R = 0.846; R² = 0.716; Adjusted R² = 0.641; F_(4,2) = 9.5; p = 0.0005

N = 20		Beta	St. Err. of Beta	B	St. Err. of B	t ₍₁₅₎	P-level
Variables	r		Intercept	-111	36,7	-3,02	0,009
Microbial Count of Neut, B/Ph	0,54	0,486	0,149	13,50	4,137	3,26	0,005
Lymphoblastes of Thymus, %	0,46	0,466	0,151	13,07	4,240	3,08	0,008
Eosinophils of Spleen, %	0,27	0,287	0,139	10,49	5,098	2,06	0,057
Macrophages of Spleen, %	-0,30	-0,527	0,144	-8,088	2,210	-3,66	0,002

R = 0.846; R² = 0.716; $\chi^2_{(4)} = 20$; p = 0.0005; Δ Prime = 0,284
 Fig. 7. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between MxDMn HRV (X-line) and Immune parameters (Y-line) in intact rats

Regression Summary for Calcitonin, ng/L
R = 0.911; R² = 0.830; Adjusted R² = 0.641; F_(10,9) = 4.4; p = 0.018

N = 20		Beta	St. Err. of Beta	B	St. Err. of B	t ₍₉₎	P-level
Variables	r		Intercept	694	302	2,30	0,047
Rod-shaped Neutrophils, %	-0,53	-0,893	0,220	-15,08	3,712	-4,06	0,003
Endotheliocytes of Thymus, %	-0,50	-0,887	0,477	-5,215	2,802	-1,86	0,096
Entropy of Thymocytogram	-0,44	1,048	0,500	202,0	96,44	2,09	0,066
Lymphocytes of Spleen, %	-0,37	-0,938	0,512	-4,198	2,293	-1,83	0,100
Bactericide Capac. of Neut., B/L	-0,32	0,576	0,300	1,568	0,815	1,92	0,087
Killing Index of Neutrophils, %	-0,31	-0,988	0,358	-2,623	0,950	-2,76	0,022
NK-Lymphocytes of Blood, %	0,57	0,611	0,224	3,473	1,273	2,73	0,023
Microphages of Spleen, %	0,30	0,292	0,188	2,824	1,819	1,55	0,155
Macrophages of Spleen, %	0,29	-0,833	0,417	-6,103	3,059	-2,00	0,077
Entropy of Splenocytogram	0,28	-1,062	0,421	-530,2	210,2	-2,52	0,033

R = 0.911; R² = 0.830; $\chi^2_{(10)} = 23$; p = 0.011; Δ Prime = 0.170
 Fig. 8. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between Calcitonin level (X-line) and Immune parameters (Y-line) in intact rats

Table 7

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or analyzed during the current study are open from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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Table 9

Regression Summary for Aldosterone, pM/L
R = 0.896; R² = 0.803; Adjusted R² = 0.627; F_(9,1) = 4.54; p = 0.013

N = 20		Beta	St. Err. of Beta	B	St. Err. of B	t ₍₁₀₎	p-level
Variables	r		Intercept	-6095	1844	-3,31	0,008
Lymphoblastes of Thymus, %	0,44	1,265	0,340	185,3	49,77	3,72	0,0040
Lymphocytes of Thymus, %	0,42	3,066	0,875	66,63	19,01	3,50	0,0057
Spleen mass Index, mg/100g	0,33	0,694	0,199	1610	462	3,48	0,0059
Plasmocytes of Spleen, %	-0,41	-0,466	0,1653	-54,26	19,27	-2,82	0,0183
Epitheliocytes of Thymus, %	-0,40	2,129	0,685	61,23	19,70	3,11	0,0111
Endotheliocytes of Thym, %	-0,39	1,523	0,507	97,86	32,56	3,01	0,0132
Macrophages of Thymus, %	-0,37	1,029	0,415	123,3	49,79	2,48	0,0327
0-Lymphocytes of Blood, %	-0,33	-0,721	0,246	-19,00	6,488	-2,93	0,0151
PMN Neutrophils of Blood, %	-0,31	-0,441	0,172	-12,63	4,922	-2,57	0,0281

R = 0.896; R² = 0.803; $\chi^2_{(9)} = 22$; p = 0.009; Λ Prime = 0.197

Fig. 9. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between Aldosterone level (X-line) and Immune parameters (Y-line) in intact rats

immunocytogram and leukocytogram in rats are regulated by sex and the neuroendocrine parameters while regulates immune parameters. Journal of Education, Health and Sport. 2020;10(7):266-288. <http://dx.doi.org/10.12775/JEHS.2020.10.07.031>

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Вперше надійшла до редакції 15.03.2026 р.
Рекомендована до друку на засіданні редакційної колегії після рецензування